

Harvesting microwave energy using pyroelectricity of nanostructured graphene/zirconium-doped hafnium oxide ferroelectric heterostructures

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Abstract

In this work, we present the design, atomistic/circuit/electromagnetic simulations, and the experimental results for graphene monolayer/zirconium-doped hafnium oxide (HfZrO) ultra-thin ferroelectric-based field effect transistors fabricated at the wafer scale, regarding the pyroelectricity generation directly from microwave signals, at room temperature and below it, namely at 218K and at 100K. The transistors work like energy harvesters, i.e., they collect low-power microwave energy and transform it into DC voltages with a maximum amplitude between 20 and 30 mV. The same devices function as microwave detectors in the band 1-10.4 GHz and at very low input power levels not exceeding 80 μ W when they are biased by using a drain voltage, with average responsivity values in the range 200-400 mV/mW.

Keywords: Energy harvesting, ferroelectrics, graphene, hafnium oxide, heterostructures, microwaves, pyroelectricity

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1. Introduction

We are living in an invisible and dense “cloud” of electromagnetic (EM) waves with different frequencies and energies, this being the direct result of the unprecedented development of wireless communications. A big portion of their spectrum is allocated in the microwave region, especially in the range 0.9-12 GHz, thus creating an ambient EM energy that is unavoidably lost if it is not transformed into a DC voltage to bias the multitude of tiny low-power electronic devices forming, among others, the Internet-of-Things (IoT) or other equipment such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc. The scientific community has been assisting tremendous advances in energy harvesting techniques using the so-called “rectennas” (i.e., rectifying antennas), which are integrated high-frequency circuits formed by an antenna (or antenna array) loaded with one or more unbiased diodes [1], [2], [3]. In this respect, thanks to their unique physical and structural properties, atomically thin materials have enhanced the performance of EM energy harvesting techniques [4].

However, other physical phenomena, like the pyroelectric effect, could be profitably exploited to supply the right amount of DC power to low-consumption electronics. In detail, the pyroelectric effect generates a time-variant current $i_p(t)$ that depends on the time-dependent variation of the temperature T , as follows: $i_p(t) = \alpha_p A dT/dt$, where A is the area of the device and α_p is the pyroelectric coefficient. So far, the pyroelectric effect is used mainly for the detection of optical signals (in the visible and infrared ranges) [5]. In contrast to the EM harvesting techniques based on rectennas (which depend on the operating frequency due to the presence of both passive and active components), the pyroelectric (as well the thermoelectric) effect is frequency independent. Pyroelectric devices do not need an antenna, which limits the frequency of operation, since they need only a variation in time of the temperature, which does not depend on the frequency of the source.

The pyroelectric effect for microwave detection was studied in the past [6] and then, it was almost abandoned due to the occurrence of semiconductors, since semiconductor-based electronic systems integrating Schottky diodes are able to detect high-frequency signals up to few THz. Now, it is

rediscovered at microwaves and millimeter-waves [7] thanks to the progress made in the domains of metamaterial absorbers and atomically thin ferroelectric materials, where pyroelectricity becomes giant [8]. Hence, the pyroelectric effect is competing with the thermoelectric one, which entails the generation of a DC voltage difference ΔV due to a temperature difference ΔT , i.e., $\Delta V = S \Delta T$, where S is the Seebeck coefficient. It has been demonstrated that, in contrast with the thermoelectric phenomenon, the pyroelectric effect has a much higher efficiency [9]. In fact, the generation of the pyroelectric current is the result of the variation of temperature in time, which can be implemented by chopping the static source of energy or directly using thermal transients, such as modulated EM sources or other transient thermal sources [10]. A comprehensive review of the pyroelectric behaviour of ferroelectric hafnium oxide-based thin films can be found in [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16].

This manuscript is dedicated to the harvesting of microwave energy using pyroelectricity in the frequency range 1-10 GHz (where almost all wireless communication systems are allocated). The pyroelectric devices under test (DUTs) are CMOS compatible ferroelectric field-effect transistors (FeFETs) having as a channel a graphene monolayer transferred on a nanometer-scale HfZrO layer. First, we present the design and fabrication of the graphene-based FeFETs. Then, we briefly explain the device operation. Next, the atomistic simulations of the DUT are detailed, together with the strategies adopted for the proposed case of study. The complete DC characterization demonstrates how atomistic simulations can reproduce the measured performance of the transistors. Finally, we provide thorough high-frequency measurements of the prototypes at room temperature and in cryogenic conditions. The main result is the generation of a DC voltage of tens of mV due to pyroelectric effect induced by amplitude-modulated microwave signals.

2. Design, fabrication, and DC measurements

(a) Design and fabrication

The cross-section of the pyroelectric graphene-based FeFET is schematically represented in Fig. 1a, whereas Fig. 1b and Fig. 1c show the top view of the whole DUT and a magnification of the FeFET area (red rectangle in Fig. 1b), respectively. To perform fast and accurate DC and high-frequency measurements, we chose a coplanar waveguide (CPW) geometry, in which the gate (G) and drain (D) are the signal lines (width of $60\ \mu\text{m}$) that can be contacted to standard CPW probe tips with pitch of $150\ \mu\text{m}$, whereas the source (S) is short-circuited to ground. The gap between the signal lines and the lateral ground planes is equal to $35\ \mu\text{m}$; in this way, a characteristic impedance of $50\ \Omega$ is guaranteed (as it is the standard reference impedance for microwave devices and components). In Fig. 1c, the main dimensions of the FeFET area are provided: the channel has the length $L_{ch} = 2500\ \text{nm}$ and the width $W_{ch} = 2000\ \text{nm}$. The transistor is in top-gate configuration and as top gate we chose a $40\ \text{nm}$ thick layer of hydrogen silsesquioxane (HSQ), which has been proven to work in an excellent manner for graphene-based active devices. The channel is a nanopatterned graphene monolayer transferred on a $6\ \text{nm}$ thick HfZrO layer grown by atomic layer deposition (ALD) directly on a 4-inch wafer of high-resistivity Si (HRSi, $500\ \mu\text{m}$ thick)/aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3 , $20\ \text{nm}$ thick). The growth of the HfZrO ferroelectric and its structural and electrical characterization are described in our previous publications [17], [18]; hence, they will be not repeated here for the sake of brevity. The graphene monolayer was transferred on HfZrO by Graphenea (San Sebastian, Spain). The Raman spectroscopy has shown that almost 80% of wafer's surface was covered with graphene monolayer, the rest being defects at the grain boundaries where graphene with different thickness values can be identified.

The graphene channel was patterned to enhance the pyroelectric properties of the heterostructure, since graphene monolayer has a high thermal conductivity (about $2000\ \text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$) that is detrimental for pyroelectric harvesting, while the nanopatterned graphene has a low thermal conductivity in the range $90\text{-}100\ \text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ [19]. Recently, it has been demonstrated that two-dimensional (2D) materials (WeSe_2) with low thermal conductivity (i.e., $3.93\ \text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$) transferred on a ferroelectric (lead strontium titanate – PZT) enhance significantly the pyroelectricity [20]. It is well known that the

periodic perforation of graphene allows opening a bandgap in graphene's dispersion relation, which is absent in pristine graphene monolayer. In this way, in nanopatterned graphene-based FETs, the carrier mobility can be tuned as a function of the length of the graphene nanomesh [21].

Fig. 1. (a) Cross-section and (b) top view of the graphene based FeFET; (c) magnification of the channel area (red rectangle in Fig. 1b).

The fabrication of the FETs on the graphene/HfZrO/Al₂O₃/HRSi substrate was performed in the following main steps (the process flow diagram summarizing the fabrication process is shown in Fig. 2a): (i) patterning of the graphene channel by electron-beam lithography (EBL) and reactive ion etching (RIE); (ii) perforation of the graphene channel using EBL (in our case, the holes have a diameter of 30 nm, whereas the horizontal and vertical distance among adjacent holes is 100 nm, Fig. 2b); (iii) patterning, metallization, and lift-off of the S and D electrodes (Cr/Au deposited using

an e-beam process); (iv) deposition of the gate dielectric (HSQ); (v) deposition of the gate electrodes (same as S and D electrodes). The resulting FeFETs are displayed in Fig. 2c. Finally, an optical lithography process was deployed for the fabrication of the CPW metallic electrodes (Fig. 2d, 10 nm thick Cr/240 nm thick Au, where the Cr was necessary as adhesion layer).

It is worth underlining that the entire fabrication of the transistors is CMOS compatible, which represents a major advantage for a large-scale exploitation of the proposed devices.

Fig. 2. (a) Process flow diagram of the fabrication process: (I) initial configuration after thin layer deposition (Al₂O₃/HfZrO/graphene), (II) polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) deposition and patterning (EBL) to define transistor's area and the holes into graphene, (III) HSQ deposition and patterning over the active area, and (IV) drain, gate, and source manufacturing by lift-off process using e-beam deposition (Cr/Au); SEM image of (b) the nanopatterned graphene channel and (c) the

graphene-based FeFET after EBL and deposition of the electrodes; (d) optical picture of the fabricated transistors.

(b) Device operation

Since FETs present a nonlinear I - V characteristic, they are suitable as microwave power detectors. Furthermore, a FET shows a better sensitivity than Schottky diodes and the output voltage, which is directly available, is proportional to the microwave power signal (at low power levels) thanks to the nonlinear I - V characteristic. In detail, Fig. 3a shows the schematic of a system comprised of an antenna and a rectifier (“rectenna”), in which the antenna provides the radiofrequency (RF) input to a rectifying diode, whose DC output voltage V_{dc} is the voltage drop on the load capacitor. A DC block capacitance and an RF choke inductance are envisaged at the input and output (respectively) of the diode to let only the DC component pass. A high-sensitivity detector typically works with RF sources located in certain positions and with a small DC voltage bias around the threshold voltage of the diode; on the contrary, an RF energy harvester collects the RF energy from unknown, distributed sources and in the absence of any DC bias voltage for the diode. The latter represents a limitation in some circumstances (e.g., when the RF power delivered to the diode is too low to allow the device to work in forward conduction). In the present case of study, we replaced the antennas with a microwave generator and, instead of a diode, we used the proposed FeFET to exploit the pyroelectric properties of the HfZrO thin film, since the pyroelectric effect is frequency independent (as mentioned in the Introduction). More specifically, sending a modulated RF signal to the gate of the transistor switches on the FeFET, and the rising and falling fronts of the microwave pulses translate into a time-dependent temperature variation that induces the generation of a pyroelectric signal at the output port (i.e., the drain), as schematically shown in Fig. 3b.

Fig. 3. (a) Generic schematic of a rectenna; (b) schematic of the operation principle of the proposed graphene-based FeFET. The microwave input (“RF in”) induces a time-dependent temperature variation dT/dt that generates $i_p(t)$. V_p is the output voltage drop on the load across which $i_p(t)$ flows.

(c) Atomistic simulations

The atomistic modelling of the graphene-based FeFETs was performed using the Q-ATK computational platform. The active region between the electrodes is composed of a single layer of graphene deposited on the top of an orthorhombic phase of HfZrO. The orthorhombic $Pca2_1$ polymorph of HfZrO is known to be a non-centrosymmetric polar phase responsible of the ferroelectric behaviour of this material [22]. For this reason, the three-dimensional unit cell of this polymorph was used to reproduce the ferroelectric behaviour of the material and to model the interface with the graphene (Fig. 4), thus estimating the impact on its characteristics. To reproduce the experimental condition, the presence of the gate electrode was replicated by using a metallic material separated from the graphene by a dielectric layer. Both these layers were treated in an implicit way (i.e., they are not characterized by an atomistic identity) by setting a dielectric constant for the dielectric gate oxide (i.e., $\epsilon_r = 3.7$ for HSQ) and different voltage values for the metallic gate electrode. A density functional theory (DFT) approach based on the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional was used to optimize the 3D structure and to extrapolate its I – V characteristics according to the Landauer formula. The single-particle wave functions were expanded on a basis of plane-wave (PW) functions, and D3 corrective terms were included [23]. We stress here

that, although I - V characteristics have been already simulated for diodes [24], [25], the effect of the gate has been never considered before, neither with semiempirical methods nor with first-principle approaches. In this respect, a three-dimensional space was defined without an atomistic identity. It was composed of a dielectric part closer to the graphene surface to mimic the HSQ, and another part upper to the first one to simulate different voltages, and then to mimic the presence and effect of a gate. In this way, the propagation of the wave function was simulated faithfully reproducing the presence of the gate observed under experimental conditions.

Fig. 4. Optimized HfZrO-graphene interface (Hf, Zr, and O atoms of FE phase are blue, light blue, and red, respectively. Graphene C atoms are in gray colour).

(d) DC measurements

The DC electrical characterization of the graphene-based FeFETs was performed on wafer at room temperature using a Keithley SCS 4200 station, by placing the DUT inside a Faraday cage and connecting the probe tips to the station with low-noise amplifiers. No fitting algorithms were used during or after measurements.

The measured curves (solid lines) for the drain current (I_D) vs. drain voltage (V_D) at several values of the gate voltage V_G , and for I_D vs. V_G at two values of V_D are compared to the simulated results (symbols) in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, respectively. In both cases, the agreement is very good. From Fig. 5a one can see that the I_D - V_D curves exhibit a nonlinear behaviour and a saturation of I_D for $V_D > 0$ V. We see in Fig. 5b that the existence of a bandgap region is confirmed by the fact that I_D attains very

low values and, thus, the transistor is in off state. The I_D-V_D characteristics obtained for different values of V_G are depicted in Fig. 6a. These results are in deep contrast with other FETs having a pristine graphene monolayer as channel: since the pristine graphene monolayer has no bandgap, the dependence of I_D on V_D at various V_G resembles a voltage-controlled linear resistor. In the present case, the extracted bandgap from the atomistic simulations is 0.37 eV, whereas from the I_D-V_G measurements we obtained a value of 0.3 eV, hence in excellent agreement with the simulated output. A quantitative analysis of the gate voltage range corresponding to the device in off state (transfer characteristic, Fig. 5b), where the Fermi level is swept across the gap of the perforated graphene/HfZrO structure, allowed us to calculate the bandgap, using the methods proposed in [22] and in [23]. From the atomistic point of view, the opening of the bandgap is due to the interaction between the asymmetric oxygen atoms of the $Pca2_1$ HfZrO polymorph and graphene (Fig. 4), which also leads to local deformations of the graphene layer. The I_D-V_G characteristics for different values of V_D are shown in Fig. 6b, from which we can observe that at low values of V_D the hysteresis loop (i.e., the imprint of the ferroelectricity) is open, meaning that the energy of the carriers is too low to reach the coercive field of HfZrO. This happens at drain voltages of 10 mV and 100 mV, corresponding to an electric field below the high value of the coercive field of HfZrO, which is in the range 1.8-1.9 MV/cm. When $V_D = 1$ V, the electric field attains the coercive field, the hysteresis loop is closed, and the subthreshold swing (SS) is switching from values beyond 60 meV to 46.8 meV, which is below the SS of CMOS FETs and this situation is displayed in Fig. 6b. However, because of the abrupt decay of I_D when V_G is swept to higher positive values, the hysteresis loop displays a small area, which means that the carriers trapped at the interface of the graphene monolayer have a quite low density.

Fig. 5. Comparison between atomistic simulations (symbols) and experimental results (solid lines) for the (a) I_D - V_D and (b) I_D - V_G curves.

Fig. 6. Measured (a) I_D - V_D characteristics at different values of V_G and (b) I_D - V_G characteristics at different values of V_D .

3. Microwave measurements

The first step was the high-frequency characterization of the graphene-based FeFETs by using a Vector Network Analyzer and performing a standard SOLT calibration to de-embed the effects of cables, connectors, and CPW probe tips in a large band up to 30 GHz. The VNA measurements were carried out at a low power level (i.e., less than -10 dBm). What we observed was a capacitor-like behaviour in terms of both reflection (S_{ii}) and transmission (S_{ij}) coefficients, where $i, j = 1, 2$ and $i \neq j$. The straightforward explanation is that we inject the microwave signal through the gate and this signal goes to the drain passing through the HSQ and graphene monolayer (and vice versa from drain to gate). In this way, the gate-HSQ-graphene structure can be seen as a metal-insulator-semimetal (MISM) capacitor, since graphene is a semimetal. A very effective way to represent this MISM capacitor is by using a lumped model constituted of a series resistance-capacitance (R - C) circuit: for the graphene monolayer, we started considering the measured surface resistance R_S of about 645Ω , obtained by means of the four-point probe (4PP) method on the graphene/HfZrO/Al₂O₃/HRSi wafer (before patterning). However, the value of R_S decreases due to the presence of the hole matrix inside the graphene layer. In detail, a reduction of R_S (due to an increase of the conductance) down to few hundreds of ohms was expected [27], [28], [29]. With the circuit of Fig. 7a (created with NI AWR Design Environment), by using the values $C \approx 15$ fF and $R = 200 \Omega$ (which are consistent with the geometry and materials of the MISM capacitor), we obtained the curves shown in Fig. 7b: the agreement with the experimental results is very good. The microwave capacitive nature of the DUT is further demonstrated in Fig. 7c, which represents the Smith chart (for the reflection coefficients): since both curves lie in the south semicircle, they correspond to a capacitor-like element.

Fig. 7. (a) Equivalent circuit model of the graphene-based FET; (b) comparison between modelled (“model”) and experimental (“exp.”) reflection (S_{ii}) and transmission (S_{ij}) coefficients; (c) Smith chart for the modelled and experimental S_{ii} coefficients.

Then, to assess the harvesting/detection capabilities of the fabricated FETs at room temperature, we used the microwave setup displayed in Fig. 8a, whereas Fig. 8b is an optical picture presenting the fabricated structures with the CPW probe tips in position for on-wafer measurements. As shown in

Fig. 8a, an amplitude-modulated (AM) microwave signal (with modulation frequency $f_{AM} = 10$ kHz) is connected to the gate of the graphene-based FeFET via a bias tee to apply the desired gate voltage V_G (attaining the values $0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm 5$ V) using a DC source, which is also connected to the drain port via a separate channel, as to provide (if necessary) the drain voltage V_D in the range $[-1, +1]$ V. The output (harvested/detected) signal is collected by the drain and read by an oscilloscope. As it can be seen from Fig. 6, a good gate control on the graphene channel conductivity was obtained. Therefore, injecting a microwave signal through the gate of the proposed FeFET allows to manipulate the conduction mechanism of the graphene channel. The obtained drain current is a function of the microwave signal amplitude and using an oscilloscope it is possible to observe the corresponding output voltage. It is known from early works [6] that AM microwave signals induce a pyroelectric response in ferroelectrics. In this respect, V_D must be kept equal to zero during the measurements, while the modulated microwave signal is pumped through the top gate.

Fig. 8. (a) Schematic of the room-temperature microwave setup; (b) optical picture of the fabricated structures with the CPW probe tips in position for on-wafer measurements.

Fig. 9a presents a single pulse of the detected (harvested) voltage V_{det} as a function of time. The measurements were performed at 1.6 GHz, with an input power of 0 dBm, $V_D = 0$ V, and $V_G = -5$ V. The arbitrary-level input square wave (50- μ s duration) is superimposed for reference as well. At the beginning of the AM microwave pulse, the HfZrO thin film absorbs the microwave power, whose main effect is the generation of transient voltages since the temperature increases and decreases due to the sub- μ s switching of the ferroelectric domains (Fig. 9a) and remains in “cold state” until the next microwave pulse is injected (Fig. 9b). The positive-sign voltage transient pulse is attributed to the rising time of the microwave pulse when the temperature is increasing, whereas the small negative-sign voltage transient pulse reflects the progressive decrease of the temperature during the remaining duration of the microwave pulse. It is worth noticing that the shape of the transient pulses can be fitted with a sech^2 function: this originates from solitons that are described by nonlinear equations and that are typical for thin film ferroelectrics [30].

Fig. 9. (a) Time response of the graphene/HfZrO FET during one microwave pulse; (b) time response of the graphene/HfZrO FETs during several microwave pulses.

Finally, we measured the same graphene-based FeFETs at 218K (i.e., -55.15°C) and at 100K (i.e., -173.15°C) using the setup presented in Fig. 10, which is similar to that used at room temperature, except for the deployment of a cryostat that includes a temperature controller and a vacuum pump. As shown in Fig. 10, the transistors were mounted on a special in-house-made test fixture to perform on-wafer temperature-dependent DC and microwave characterization.

Fig. 10. Microwave setup for cryogenic measurements.

The best results were obtained at 2 GHz (the measured maximum frequency for harvesting being up to 27 GHz) and the voltage transients at different input microwave power levels P_{in} are presented in Fig. 11a for $V_D = 0\text{ V}$ and $V_G = -5\text{ V}$. Increasing the input power leads to an increase of the amplitude of the transient voltage pulses, as an expected effect of the time-dependent variation of the temperature associated to the rising and falling fronts of the microwave signal. Even if this phenomenon occurs at any temperature, a (predicted) signal distortion was observed at high input power values due to the nonlinearities of the DUT. The voltage responsivity R_V is displayed in Fig. 11b as a function of the delivered power $P_{del} = P_{in} (1 - |S_{11}|^2)$, which is the effective power in input at the gate considering the impedance mismatch. The responsivity exhibits an average value of 400 mV/mW, which is very high for low microwave power not exceeding 125 μW . When lowering

the temperature to 100K, the shape of the pulse transient changes dramatically, but an average responsivity of 100 mV/mW in the same range of microwave power can still be achieved.

Fig. 11. (a) Time response at 2 GHz and 218K, without any applied drain voltage and gate voltage equal to -5 V; (b) voltage responsivity at 2 GHz and 218K depending on the microwave power.

If we bias the drain electrode, the entire device works as a microwave detector. For example, working at room temperature with $V_D = 0.5$ V and $V_G = -5$ V the average responsivity is 300 mV/mW at 1 GHz for $P_{det} \leq 35$ μ W (Fig. 12a); at 10.4 GHz the average responsivity is 80 mV/mW with P_{det} not exceeding 80 μ W (Fig. 12b).

Fig. 12. Voltage responsivity of the graphene/HfZrO FET working as microwave detector at room temperature with drain voltage of 0.5 V and gate voltage of -5 V at (a) 1 GHz and (b) 10.4 GHz.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented the design, simulations, and experimental characterization of a graphene/HfZrO FET with a perforated channel, able to work as both (i) a pyroelectric harvester under the effect of a time-dependent temperature variation induced by a modulated microwave signal and (ii) a room-temperature microwave detector with high voltage responsivity with the application of a small DC bias voltage. An articulated atomistic approach was used to model the transistor and to simulate its electronic transport properties. The use of the combined computational-experimental approach allowed us to correlate the calculated and measured properties of the DUT with the short- and long-range phenomena observed on the interfaces at atomistic level. Moreover, this approach led to information that can be difficult to obtain with a pure experimental approach, and which could be helpful for other fabrication processes. The measurements were performed in the case of the pyroelectric harvester at room temperature and in cryogenic conditions, namely at 218K and at 100K, and the main result was the generation of a DC voltage of tens of mV due to pyroelectric effect induced by the amplitude-modulated microwave signal. The shape of the transient pulses can be fitted

with a sech^2 function, which originates from solitons that are described by nonlinear equations and that are typical for thin film ferroelectrics.

The microwave detection properties were assessed at room temperatures with good responsivity values of over 10000 mV/mW observed for very low input microwave power levels, thus showing that the proposed device is suitable for both pyroelectric harvesting and detection applications.

The proposed graphene/HfZrO-based FETs represent a promising candidate for CMOS-compatible nanoelectronics devices with enhanced multi-functionalities coming from the seamless integration of nanoscale materials.

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References

- [1] Costanzo A, Dionigi M, Masotti D, Mongiardo M, Monti G, Tarricone L and Sorrentino R 2014 *Proc. IEEE* **102** 1692, DOI: 10.1109/JPROC.2014.2355261.
- [2] Kanaujia B K, Singh N and Kumar S 2021 *Springer Singapore*, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-16-2536-7.
- [3] Gu X, Hemour S and Wu K 2022 *Proc. IEEE* **110** 56, DOI: 10.1109/JPROC.2021.3127930.
- [4] Aldrigo M, Dragoman M, Pelagalli N, Laudadio E, Zappelli L, Iordanescu S, Vasilache D, Dinescu A, Pierantoni L, Stipa P and Mencarelli D 2022 *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.* **70** 1132, DOI: 10.1109/TMTT.2021.3129520.

- [5] Velarde G, Pandya S, Karthik J, Pesquera D and Martin L W 2021 *APL Materials* **9** 010702, DOI: 10.1063/5.0035735.
- [6] White D J and Wieder H H 1963 *J. Appl. Phys.* **34** 2487, DOI: 10.1063/1.1702770.
- [7] Fan K, Stenger V and Padilla W J 2022 *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **121** 021701, DOI: 10.1063/5.0094201.
- [8] Jiang J, Zhang L, Ming C, Zhou H, Bose P, Guo Y, Hu Y, Wang B, Chen Z, Jia R, Pendse S, Xiang Y, Xia Y, Lu Z, Wen X, Cai Y, Sun C, Wang G-C, Lu T-M, Gall D, Sun Y-Y, Koratkar N, Fohtung E, Shi Y and Shi J 2022 *Nature* **607** 480, DOI: 10.1038/s41586-022-04850-7.
- [9] Sebald G, Guyomar D and Agbossou A 2019 *Smart Mater. Struct.* **18** 125006, DOI: 10.1088/0964-1726/18/12/125006.
- [10] Hanrahan B, Smith A and Bhatia B 2022 *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **120** 120503, DOI: 10.1063/5.0085949.
- [11] Hoffmann M, Schroeder U, Künneth C, Kersch A, Starschich S, Böttger U and Mikolajick T 2015 *Nano Energy* **18** 154.
- [12] Smith S W, Kitahara A R, Rodriguez M A, Henry M D, Brumbach M T and Ihlefeld J F 2017 *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **110** 072901, DOI: 10.1063/1.4976519.
- [13] Jachalke S, Schenk T, Park M H, Schroeder U, Mikolajick T, Stöcker H, Mehner E and Meyer D C 2018 *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **112** 142901, DOI: 10.1063/1.5023390.
- [14] Hanrahan B, Mart C, Kämpfe T, Czernohorsky M, Weinreich W and Smith A 2019 *Energy Technol.* **7** 1900515, DOI: 10.1002/ente.201900515.
- [15] Mart C, Kämpfe T, Kühnel K, Czernohorsky M, Kolodinski S, Wiatr M, Weinreich W and Eng L M 2021 *APL Materials* **9** 051120, DOI: 10.1063/5.0051329.
- [16] Neuber M, Lederer M W, Mertens K, Kämpfe T, Czernohorsky M and Seidel K 2022 *Crystals* **12** 1115; DOI: 10.3390/cryst12081115.
- [17] Dragoman M, Aldrigo M, Dragoman D, Iordanescu S, Dinescu A and Modreanu M 2021 *Phys. Status Solidi RRL* **15** 2000521, DOI: 10.1002/pssr.202000521.

- [18] Dragoman M, Aldrigo M, Dragoman D, Iordanescu S, Dinescu A, Vulpe S and Modreanu M 2022 *Crit. Rev. Solid State Mater. Sci.*, DOI: 10.1080/10408436.2022.2083579.
- [19] Pyun K R and Ko S H 2019 *Mater. Today Energy* **12** 431, DOI: 10.1016/j.mtener.2019.04.008.
- [20] Mbisike S C, Eckart L, Phair J W, Lomax P and Cheung R 2022 *J. Appl. Phys.* **131** 144101, DOI: 10.1063/5.0086216.
- [21] Dragoman M, Dinescu A and Dragoman D 2018 *Phys. E: Low-Dimens. Syst. Nanostructures* **97** 296, DOI: 10.1016/j.physe.2017.12.011.
- [22] Tao L L, Paudel T R, Kovalev A A and Tsymbal E Y 2017 *Phys. Rev. B* **95** 245141, DOI: 10.1103/PhysRevB.95.245141
- [23] Grimme S, Ehrlich S and Goerigk L 2011 *J. Comput. Chem.* **32** 1456, DOI: 10.1002/jcc.21759.
- [24] Al-Dirini F, Hossain F M, Nirmalathas A and Skafidas E 2014 *Sci. Rep.* **4** 3983, DOI: 10.1038/srep03983.
- [25] Al-Dirini F, Hossain F M, Mohammed M A, Hossain Md S, Nirmalathas A and Skafidas E 2016 *J. Appl. Phys.* **119** 044506, DOI: 10.1063/1.4940707.
- [26] Dragoman M, Dinescu A and Dragoman D 2017 *Nanotechnology* **28** 015201, DOI: 10.1088/0957-4484/28/1/015201.
- [27] Wei T, Bao L, Hauke F and Hirsch A 2020 *ChemPlusChem* **85** 1655, DOI: 10.1002/cplu.202000419.
- [28] Wei T, Hauke F and Hirsch A 2021 *Adv. Mater.* **33** 2104060, DOI: 10.1002/adma.202104060.
- [29] Xiong W, Zhou Y S, Hou W J, Jiang L J, Gao Y, Fan L S, Jiang L, Silvain J F and Feng Lu Y 2014 *Sci. Rep.* **4** 4892, DOI: 10.1038/srep04892.
- [30] Hubert M B, Justin M, Kudryashov N A, Betchewe G, Douvagai and Doka S Y 2018 *Phys. Scr.* **93** 075201, DOI: 10.1088/1402-4896/aac407.